

A Study of Implementation Status of School Infrastructure Facilities among Upper Primary Schools of Various Boards

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Abstract

The school infrastructure facilities enhance the learning of learner and teaching effectiveness of a teacher in the classroom. With the enactment of many schemes to ensure infrastructure facilities as Operation Blackboard, Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan and RTE Act 2009 have been launched so far. Currently, the provisions of 'Right of Children to Free and Compulsory Education Act 2009' are followed in elementary education all over the country. Present research article tries to investigate the infrastructure facilities in upper primary schools of various boards mentioned in RTE Act 2009. Investigator selected 50 upper primary schools to investigate. Data was collected through self-made questionnaire. Results of study reveal that implementation status of many provisions of RTE Act 2009 related to school infrastructure facilities were found very weak.

Keywords: Implementation Status, Infrastructure facilities, RTE Act 2009, Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan, Upper primary schools

Background of the Study

Education is central to human civilization generally considered to be the backbone of national ideals. It shapes the entire thinking process of human race. The things learned inside and outside the class room exerts a great influence on the attitude, personality, work habits and values of the learner. The Education Commission (1964-66), the very aptly began its report with these words, *“the destiny of India is now being shaped in her classrooms.”* The NPE (1986) also observed, *“The country has reached a stage in its economic and technical development when a major effort must be made to derive the maximum benefit from the assets already created and to ensure that the fruits of change reach all sections. Education is highway to the goal.”* According to thinkers in ancient India, knowledge and education was considered as integral part and it was viewed as the ‘third eye’ of man, which was responsible for insight in to all affairs and it teaches him how to act; it leads to salvation in the mundane sphere and all-round progress and prosperity. Mahatma Gandhi, the great leader of Indian revolution, aptly remarked that *“area of education and life should be same, means education should be directly related to life and should enable a person to tackle the problems of his/her day-to-day life, rationally and skillfully.”*

RTE Act 2009 is a broad Act which focuses on many dimensions of elementary education but the researcher tried to investigate the current status only the provisions related to infrastructure facilities in upper primary schools mentioned in RTE Act 2009. Many studies also have done to investigate the implementation status of RTE Act provisions. **Krishan, A. H., Teja, K. R. & Ravindra, K. (2020)** conducted a study on ‘Implementation Status of Right to Education (RTE) Act 2009 in Andhra Pradesh: An Empirical Analysis’. Research revealed that majority of students responded positively regarding teaching-learning quality indicators and provisions. The RTE Act has achieved success in achieving some of the goals with which it started in the year 2010. **Kar, N. (2019)** conducted a study on ‘A Study on Right to Education (RTE) Act 2009 and its Compliance in Schools of Golaghat District of Assam’. Findings of the study revealed that the majority of schools in Golaghat district had very less provisions for visually impaired and children’s Magazines, Newspapers and other kinds of books in library were missing. Running water facility was not adequate to hygiene purpose. Most of the schools had no separate classrooms and basic facilities like separate room for headmaster, staffroom

for teachers, computer room, sport equipment and space for assembly. **Parveen, R. (2018)** conducted a study entitled ‘Implementation of RTE Act a case Study of two Gram Panchayats in Karnataka.’ It was found that RTE in true spirit was not being implemented as there was a heavy inflow of private players in the field of education and that commercialization of education. So, the concept of free as a right of child was totally nullified on the ground. **Senapati, K. (2018)** conducted a study on ‘Right to Education Act Challenges in its Implementation in rural area of Burdwan District: A Survey Study’. The findings of the study showed that children in rural area had faced many obstacles in primary education. School infrastructure was of medium level and fifty percent teachers supported that student taught by psychological compliant procedure.

Objectives of the Study

- To find out the current implementation status of infrastructure facilities in upper primary schools.
- To find out the gaps in implementation of infrastructure facilities in upper primary schools.
- To recommend the suggestions for fine implementations of infrastructure facilities in upper primary schools.

Methodology

Population

The population included upper primary schools located in District Sambhal of Uttar Pradesh running under control Basic Shiksha Parishad, Madhya Shiksha Parishad and CBSE.

Sample and Sampling Technique

The investigator selected 50 upper primary schools randomly to investigate the current implementation status of infrastructure facilities.

Research Tool

The investigator used self-made questionnaire for collect the data. The tool included 15 items related to infrastructure facilities mentioned in RTE Act 2009.

Statistical Treatment

To analyze the collect data percentage method was used.

Data Analysis

Implementation Status related to school infrastructure

It is further divided school infrastructure facilities into following sub-dimensions to make clear analysis of data-

(a). Availability of infrastructure

Following infrastructure facilities should be available according to RTE Act 2009 in the schools for the free and compulsory education of children aged 6 to 14 years. Table 1.0 shows the current availability of infrastructure facilities in Basic Shiksha Parishad, Madhyamik and CBSE upper primary schools.

Table 1.0: Percentage of availability of infrastructure

Statements	Board %		
	Basic	Madhyamik	CBSE
1. Whether the school building is in good condition?	76.47	100	100
2. Whether school has boundary wall?	76.47	95.45	100

findings- 100% of Madhyamik and CBSE board school and 76.47% of Basic upper primary school building were in good condition. There was availability of boundary wall in 76.47% Basic schools, 95.45% Madhyamik schools and 100% CBSE schools.

Fig. 1.0: Showing percentage of implementation status of RTE Act provisions Board wise in sub-dimension (a)

From the above analysis it can be concluded that school building of Basic Shiksha Parishad need improvement. Because school building ensures the security of children and creates good teaching-learning environment.

(b). Availability of facilities

According to RTE Act 2009, following facilities should be available in the schools for imparting quality education. Table 2.0 shows percentage of Board wise, Institute wise and locality wise facilities available in the school.

Table 2.0: Percentage of current availability facilities

Statements	Board %		
	Basic	Madhyamik	CBSE
1. Whether school has barrier free access to all?	94.11	100	100
2. Whether school has separate toilet facility for boys and girls?	94.11	95.45	100
3. Is there available safe drinking water facility in the school?	76.47	100	100
4. Whether school has playground?	82.35	81.81	100
5. Whether school has library with books?	58.82	77.27	100
6. Is there functional science laboratory in the school?	35.29	63.63	72.72
7. Whether school has equipment for games?	64.70	86.36	100

Findings- findings are presented under following heads-

- i. Barrier free access-** 94.11% upper primary schools of Basic Shiksha Parishad have barrier free access where as 100% upper primary schools of Madhyamik and CBSE Board schools have barrier free access.
- ii. Separate toilet facility-** 94.11% of schools of Basic Shiksha Parishad have separate toilet facility for boys and girls where as 95.45% schools of Madhyamik and 100% of CBSE schools have separate toilet facility for boys and girls.
- iii. Safe drinking water facility-** Facility of safe drinking water was available in 76.47% Basic Shiksha Parishad upper primary schools, 100% Madhyamik and CBSE board upper primary schools.
- iv. Playground in the schools-** 82.35% of schools of Basic upper primary schools, 81.81% Madhyamik and 100% CBSE Board schools have the facility of playground.

- v. **Library with books-** 58.82% upper primary schools of Basic Shiksha Parishad whereas it was found 77.27% and 100% in Madhyamik and CBSE upper schools respectively.
- vi. **Science laboratory-** The science laboratory was available in 35.29% Basic Shiksha Parishad upper primary schools, 63.63% Madhyamik and 72.72% CBSE upper primary schools.
- vii. **Equipment for games-** The equipment for games were available in 64.70% Basic Shiksha Parishad and 86.36% Madhyamik upper primary schools but it was found 100% in CBSE upper primary schools.

Fig. 2.0: Showing percentage of implementation status of sub-dimension (b) related to RTE Act provisions Board wise

From the above analysis it can be concluded that Basic schools were needed to improve for barrier free access, safe drinking water, libraries, science laboratories and equipment for games. There was felt a need for improvement of playground, library, science laboratory and equipment for games in Madhyamik upper primary schools whereas CBSE upper primary schools needed for science laboratory to all

round development and create quality of teaching-learning environment in upper primary schools.

(c). Facilities for disabled children

According to RTE Act 2009 every school must have the facilities for disabled children for inclusion of every child in teaching learning process. Following table 3.0 displays the percentage of current availability of facilities related to disabled children.

Table 3.0: Percentage of facilities for disabled children

Statements	Board %		
	Basic	Madhyamik	CBSE
1. Whether ramp is available for disabled students?	82.35	45.45	27.27
2. Are there equipment available for children with special need in the school?	5.88	9.09	45.45

Findings- Availability of ramp for disabled children was available in 82.35% Basic Shiksha Parishad, 45.45% Madhyamik and 27.27% CBSE upper primary schools. 5.88% Basic, 9.09% Madhyamik and 45.45% CBSE upper primary schools have the equipment for children with special need.

Fig. 3.0: Showing percentage of implementation status of sub-dimension (c) related to RTE Act provisions Board wise

From the above analysis it can be concluded that the current status of facilities for disabled children is very poor in all boards. Facilities for disabled children are necessary for inclusive schools. So, government and related authorities should focus on facilities related to disabled children for the purpose of education to every child.

(d). Utility items

There are many provisions in RTE Act 2009 to ensure certain facilities for security and daily need. The Table 4.0 given below shows percentage of current availability of utility items.

Table 4.0: Percentage of utility item

Statements	Board %		
	Basic	Madhyamik	CBSE
1. Whether school has First Aid box?	64.70	86.36	100
2. Is fire extinguisher available in the school?	76.47	100	100
3. Whether the furniture is available for students sitting?	41.17	95.45	100
4. Whether electricity and electric fans are available in the school?	29.41	81.81	100

Findings- findings are presented under following heads-

- i. First Aid Box-** 64.70% Basic Shiksha Parishad, 86.36% Madhyamik and 100% CBSE upper primary schools have First Aid Box.
- ii. Fire Extinguisher-** Fire extinguisher was available in 76.47% Basic Shiksha Parishad, 100% Madhyamik and CBSE upper primary schools.
- iii. Furniture for student sitting-** 41.17% Basic Shiksha Parishad, 95.45% Madhyamik Shiksha Parishad and 100% CBSE have the furniture for student sitting.

iv. **Electricity and electric fans-** The analysis of data shows that electricity and electric fans were available in 29.41% Basic, 81.81% Madhyamik and 100% CBSE upper primary schools.

Fig. 4.0: Showing percentage of implementation status of sub-dimension (d) related to RTE Act provisions Board wise

After analysis it can be concluded that there was need of First Aid Box and Fire extinguisher in Basic and Madhyamik whereas furniture for student sitting and electricity were needed in Basic and Madhyamik.

Suggestions for effective implementation of infrastructure facilities

After getting final findings the researcher has framed following suggestions for all stakeholders associated with RTE Act 2009 in any form.

- Appropriate government, school and local authority should focus firstly on fulfillment infrastructural facilities in all the schools. It will help strengthen the fundamental learning of students.
- Government should focus on implementation infrastructural facilities mentioned in RTE Act 2009.

- School and society should place your demand for infrastructural facilities before public leaders and responsible authorities.
- Parents should ensure infrastructural facilities during admitting their children in any school.
- Basic Shiksha Parishad and Madhyamik Shiksha Parishad needed more improvement to arrange academic infrastructure.
- Responsible authorities should provide affiliation to any educational body after fulfillment all the infrastructure facilities.
- Government should prevent the gaps in implementation and flow of fund.

Conclusion

In the present article it was tried to investigate the current implementation status of infrastructural facilities among upper primary schools of various boards. The results reveal that the infrastructural facilities as building conditions of the schools, boundary wall, sanitation facilities, safe drinking water facility, playground in the school, library, science laboratory, first aid box, fire extinguisher, furniture and electric connection were not properly implemented so far. In the modern time the imagine can not be of effective teaching-learning without proper infrastructure facilities. So, provide education to all with inclusive approach it is very necessary for every responsible authority to manage qualitative infrastructure facilities in every elementary school.

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